

Polyglutamine disease in peripheral tissues

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Introduction

There are at least nine different neurodegenerative diseases caused by polyglutamine expansion, including Huntington's disease (HD), dentatorubral-pallidoluysian atrophy (DRPLA), spinobulbar muscular atrophy (SBMA), spinocerebellar ataxia type 1 (SCA1), type 2 (SCA2), type 3 (SCA3 or Machado- Joseph disease (MJD1)), type 6 (SCA6), type 7 (SCA7), and type 17 (SCA17). All of these diseases occur by expansion of the trinucleotide repeat CAG which encodes a glutamine (Q) tract in their respective proteins (Figure 1). However, there are no other conserved motifs in the disease associated proteins. Notably, all of these disorders are inherited dominantly and while there is some correlation between the number of repeats and the severity of symptoms, by and large there is much heterogeneity in the clinical phenotypes¹. Clinically, these phenotypes include loss of medium spiny neurons in the striatum of the brain, leading to progressive loss of motor control, cognitive decline, and neuropsychosis. At a cellular level, accumulation of these mutant polyQ proteins leads to formation of insoluble protein aggregates that impair vital cellular processes like autophagy, axonal transport, endocytosis, and proteostasis²⁻⁴. These aggregates have been known to localize to a wide variety of different tissues outside of the central nervous system (CNS)^{5,6}. Growing evidence indicates that these peripheral tissues can contribute to the symptoms of the disease. Moreover, differences in the health of

peripheral tissues may explain the variation in symptoms between patients, and systemic signalling from these tissues could influence the progression of the disease in the nervous system⁷⁻¹⁰. Here, studies of *Drosophila melanogaster* polyglutamine disease models are reviewed, and the emerging evidence on the biological consequences in peripheral tissues from various animal models of polyglutamine disease are discussed. To conclude, new perspectives on polyglutamine disease research are addressed.

Polyglutamine in *Drosophila*

Like many other examples throughout the history of *Drosophila* research, polyglutamine disease was thought to be a phenomenon that did not occur in flies. Although at least 25 *Drosophila* genes harbour glutamine repeats¹¹, none have been observed to expand natively in the fly. This was until the Bonini and Zipursky labs each demonstrated with independent SCA3 and HD humanized fly models that indeed flies are susceptible to polyglutamine disease^{12,13}. By utilizing a non-vital tissue like the fly eye they were able to induce degeneration without killing the animal, which established precedent for numerous neurodegeneration studies that followed¹⁴⁻¹⁶. In the eye the loss of photoreceptors, the collapse of the ommatidial structure and the presence of polyQ aggregates can be quantified to assess severity. Varying degrees of severity were observed, which is amenable for screening for genetic modifiers that either enhance or suppress the degenerative phenotype. Since then numerous different constructs have been built to introduce polyQ repeats into the fly including N-terminal fragments of huntingtin (Htt)^{12,17}, C-terminal fragments of ataxin-3¹³, naked polyQ tracts¹⁸, epitope tagged polyQ tracts^{18,19}, and the full length ataxin-1 gene²⁰. It is still

not completely understood how the repeats result in toxicity, but it can be alleviated either by preventing aggregates²¹ or by preventing the pathogenic effects of the aggregates leading to improvement of degenerative symptoms^{19,22}. *Drosophila* models have contributed greatly to what we currently know. For some time it remained unclear whether pathology was caused by deleterious effects unique to each disease protein or to a common toxicity mediated by the polyQ repeats themselves. In flies, it was shown that expressing naked polyQ repeats alone is enough to cause pathogenic effects^{18,19}. The associated lethality was found to be highly dependent on the cell type in which the repeats are expressed¹⁸. Furthermore, when the same number of repeats were built into *Dishevelled (Dsh)*, a protein with a polyQ tract in its N-terminal domain, the construct was actually found to partially rescue a lethal null *Dsh* allele. Evidently, the protein context is important for polyQ repeat toxicity¹⁸. Deciphering what differentiates repeats that lead to disease and those that do not remains an unanswered question in polyglutamine research.

By identifying suppressors or enhancers of the toxicity it helps better understand the molecular underpinnings that lead to aggregate formation and pathogenesis. As well, it provides potential genes or pathways to target with pharmaceuticals in patients to slow the progression of the disease or ameliorate symptoms. Furthermore, in many ways detailed studies of these modifier genes in the context of human disease models can provide more information about certain fundamental cellular pathways than loss-of-function studies. In disease studies, more striking phenotypes can be revealed which can give unanticipated insight into the cognate function of these genes that may be harder to glean from classical genetic approaches, which use mutations that may be

lethal or have a non-specific phenotype²³. Many genetic screens have identified modifiers of polyglutamine toxicity and revealed a long list of genes that span a wide array of different types of molecules: transcription factors^{20,24}, RNA binding proteins^{20,25,26}, histone acetylases/ deacetylases¹⁷, ubiquitin/ proteasome system proteins^{20,27,28}, autophagy/ lysosome system proteins^{28,29}, chaperones and co-chaperones^{19,22}.

Evidence of Polyglutamine disease in peripheral tissues

The formation of protein aggregates is generally understood to be a main characteristic of polyglutamine disease pathogenesis. While aggregates can form in many tissues outside of the nervous system, because peripheral tissues are often neglected, the extent to how the aggregates influence these tissues and how they contribute to the overall disease is unknown. Also, it is unknown whether aggregates are capable of forming in every tissue where the pathogenic protein is expressed. In addition, it cannot be excluded that the nature of the aggregates may differ across tissues.

Evidence from animal models has been key to better understanding the disease on a more systemic level. Knock-in mouse models facilitate the determination of the tissues in which the aggregates form⁶. In the fly, using the UAS/GAL4 system allows a pathogenic construct to be driven in any tissue, which allows us to see how aggregates form and potentially observe different aggregate morphologies³⁰. The unique advantage of the *Drosophila* model is the ease to restrict the expression in specific tissues with a simple genetic cross without expression in any other tissue. Here, we include a comprehensive review of all tissues that have been described to have symptoms and dysfunction, as well as which tissues have displayed aggregates

and their morphology (Figure 2). Polyglutamine disease symptoms in peripheral tissues have been exhaustively reviewed by other groups ^{7,10}.

Bone

Bone density loss has been reported in patients with Huntington's disease, as well as in mouse models ^{31,32}. The reason for declines in bone density is unclear. It is possible that it could be a side-effect of treatments or immobility, or perhaps from the disease itself. It is known that pre-HD carriers were found to have significantly lower bone density compared to healthy individuals ³³. Also loss of bone density is often accompanied by disruptions in endocrine signalling, such as increased cortisol levels. Indeed, in HD mouse models with decreased bone mineral density, they also displayed increased cortisol concentrations. Similarly, in HD patients elevated urinary cortisol has been observed ³¹. Currently, bone has not been examined for presence of protein aggregates.

Gut

In recent years there has been accumulating evidence on gut microbiota and the gut-brain axis in health and disease. Neurodegenerative disease is no exception, with findings that indicate gut dysbiosis may influence pathogenic processes, and thus the progression of various neurological diseases ³⁴. In particular, in HD patients significant differences have been found in the gut microbial communities compared to healthy controls ³⁵. Moreover, among HD patients correlations between the kind of gut bacteria and cognitive performance were observed. In addition, in patients with advanced stages of the disease gastroesophageal inflammation has been noted to have increased prevalence ³⁶. In HD mice, significant differences in gut microbiota have been

observed compared to wildtype controls. These differences were found to correlate with difficulties with weight gain and motor impairments³⁷. Furthermore, in HD flies the presence of *E.coli* in the gut has been found to aggravate disease pathogenesis including protein aggregation in the brain, mobility, and longevity³⁸. Protein aggregates have been observed throughout the stomach wall, duodenum and rectum of HD mice⁶.

Liver

Hepatic dysfunction has been observed in HD patients as well as mouse models. The liver plays a critical role in the removal of toxins and maintaining plasma glucose concentrations, both of which are impaired in HD. Clinical findings show elevated lactate concentrations in the blood of patients^{39,40}. These studies are corroborated by findings from an HD mouse model which also found higher lactate, as well as reduced hepatic glucose output and indications of reduced gluconeogenesis⁴¹. In addition, in two mouse models of HD the urea cycle has been demonstrated to be impaired as a result of decreased transcription of urea cycle enzymes, causing hyperammonemia⁴². Cellularly, liver mitochondrial dysfunction is also evident in both symptomatic patients and pre-symptomatic carriers^{43,44}. Aggregates have been observed throughout the hepatocytes and bile duct epithelium^{5,6}.

Kidney and Adrenal glands

Evidence of renal and adrenal dysfunction is evident in polyQ disease. In patients with DRPLA, glomerular sclerosis and perivascular fluid collections are evident in the kidney, as well as hypoalbuminemia due to increased urinary protein excretion⁴⁵. In HD mice, progressive alterations in the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis have been

observed which resemble Cushing's syndrome. The adrenal glands of these mice were enlarged and there was hypersecretion of adreno-corticotrophic hormone and corticosterone in serum and urine. This correlated with increased urinary cortisol in HD patients³¹. HD aggregates are observed throughout the kidney in the cortex, medulla and papilla, in tubule/ duct epithelium, interstitial cells, and some glomerular cells⁶. Aggregates are also present in the adrenal glands in the outer and inner cortex and medulla, with a greater density in the cortex⁶.

Pancreas

It has been noted that there is a higher prevalence of diabetes mellitus in patients with HD⁴⁶. HD mice display elevated plasma glucose levels, as well as reduced hypoglycaemic response to insulin^{31,47}. Immunocytochemical staining of the islets reveal glucagon and insulin content to be reduced⁴⁷. Protein aggregates are present in the nucleus of pancreatic islets in mouse models⁶.

Heart

Epidemiological studies have shown heart disease to be the second leading cause of death in patients with HD^{48,49}. Clinical findings have ascribed cardiac impairments to dysfunction of the autonomic nervous system (ANS). Mouse models of HD have revealed unstable heart beats and arrhythmia, as well as reduced heart size^{50,51}. Cellular changes to the cardiac tissue have also been observed. Changes to cardiomyocytes of HD mice in mitochondrial ultrastructure and dynamics have been observed. As well, aggregates have been detected in the cardiac muscle fibres⁶. In vivo fly models corroborate such findings. Ultrastructural analysis of HD fly heart show

myofibrillar and mitochondrial defects, increased ROS, and the presence of protein aggregates⁵².

Adipose tissue

Several lines of evidence have shown another prominent peripheral manifestation of HD in patients is unintended weight loss⁵³⁻⁵⁵, for which a decline in fat mass is a known contributor³². Adipose tissue secretes a wide range of endocrine protein factors called adipokine hormones, which include leptin and adiponectin. These factors are involved in regulating energy metabolism and body weight⁵⁶. HD patients as well as two different HD mouse models have been shown to have reduced levels of circulating leptin^{57,58}. Since adipose tissue is a major source of leptin, loss of fat mass also exacerbates weight loss. Loss of body mass has also been hypothesized to contribute to the rate of progression of the disease. Indeed weight loss accompanies several metabolic changes in patients as well. These changes include nutritional deficiencies^{59,60}, glucose imbalance and insulin resistance⁶¹⁻⁶³. It is important to note that weight loss and metabolic symptoms are not simply a secondary effect of widespread neurodegeneration. In fact, in a *Drosophila* HD model where a polyglutamine expanded Htt transgene was expressed exclusively in the fat body, flies displayed chronic weight loss despite higher caloric intake, decreased longevity, decreased lipid droplets, and accumulation of protein aggregates⁶⁴. Taken together these findings indicate that expression of mHtt in the fat is sufficient for metabolic abnormalities, independent of any neurodegeneration.

Muscle

Although HD is considered a neurodegenerative disease, many of the outward symptoms, such as muscle wasting and chorea, influence the muscle. As such many groups have started trying to discern whether these symptoms in the muscle occur as a result of widespread neurodegeneration, or could contribute to the pathology independently⁶⁵. There is much evidence to suggest the latter. Toxic protein aggregates have been observed in the muscles of mouse, fly and worm HD models, as well as in the muscles of HD patients^{5,6,66-70}. In worms, expression of a polyQ Htt construct in the body wall muscles results in delayed development, motor impairment, and reduced lifespan⁶⁹. Expression of a polyglutamine expanded ataxin-3 construct in the muscle of the fly was observed to result in lethality, while expressing the same construct in the nervous system gave viable adults¹³. Finally, clinical data have shown that myopathy markers are observed, and muscle performance declined many years before first signs of chorea were diagnosed⁷¹. In a companion preprint, we describe a muscle model of HD in the fly³⁰. We demonstrate that not only does the expression of a pathogenic construct result in detrimental phenotypes like reduced longevity, locomotion and the presence of aggregates, we also show that there are different modes of pathogenicity in the muscle. These different modes are identified by strikingly different protein aggregate distributions, which result in differing severity of symptoms (Barwell et al in press). Furthermore, numerous different muscle specific signalling pathways have been identified to either suppress or enhance polyglutamine disease symptoms. Myocyte Enhancer Factor 2 (Mef2) is a gene necessary for myofiber development and homeostasis⁷²⁻⁷⁴. It has been shown to have impaired function in polyglutamine disease, becoming sequestered in intranuclear inclusions in the skeletal

muscle⁷⁵. SBMA and HD mouse models have shown that it is the diminished expression of Mef2 that underlies the muscle atrophy associated with these polyQ diseases⁷⁵. Myostatin is a member of the transforming growth factor- β family, widely known as a negative regulator of muscle growth⁷⁶. In an HD model, inhibition of myostatin suppressed weight loss, muscle atrophy, weakening and motor impairments⁷⁷. Scn4a is a subunit of the skeletal muscle sodium voltage-gated channel, as such it has an important role in generating and propagating action potentials. Mutations in Scn4a are associated with various neuromuscular disorders⁷⁸. In a recent screen, Scn4a was identified as an enhancer of HD, exacerbating the shortened lifespan, weight loss, and mitochondrial morphological defects⁷⁹. These findings could implicate involvement of muscle specific signalling in disease pathology.

New perspectives on polyglutamine disease research

Numerous genes have been identified to modify polyglutamine disease symptoms. However, just because a gene modifies symptoms does not necessarily imply it is involved in disease pathology. All the aforementioned muscle-specific genetic modifiers are natively involved in the development, maintenance, and function of the muscle. Therefore, altering their expression could simply be compensating for the muscle wasting and weakening symptoms that come as a result of the disease. For instance, while inhibiting myostatin in a diseased animal may improve muscle atrophy, in a wildtype animal it famously causes a hypertrophic muscle phenotype. While identifying genes to treat symptoms is undeniably beneficial therapeutically, if the goal is to understand the etiology our approach should be adapted. Depending on whether we aim to treat the disease or improve quality of life changes the types of screens we

should perform. Screening for genes that modify the amount of aggregates are beneficial in slowing disease progression and onset of symptoms. Screening for genes that do not change the aggregates but improve all other disease symptoms, have the potential to aid in understanding how the aggregates confer toxicity. In this issue, we describe a muscle model of HD in the fly. For the first time, we demonstrate how the protein aggregates can take on different distributions, and this influences the severity of disease symptoms. With this model it opens up a whole new avenue in which to screen for genetic modifiers of disease. This model offers the ability to screen for genes that change the shape or distribution of the aggregates. Now, not only would we have the ability to identify genes that take away the aggregates, but also an ability to identify the genes that regulate and control the biochemical nature of the aggregates. The fact that this correlates with symptom severity also allows us to understand the genetics factors underlying how they form and arrange and why certain distributions are more detrimental than others. Symptoms like behaviour or lifespan can also be screened to determine the mechanisms behind what makes symptoms bad or worse. In our model, we also find that a previously identified suppressor of polyglutamine toxicity in the nervous system produced little to no effect in muscle. This work reveals that peripheral tissues contribute to the disease with distinct genetic mechanisms than the nervous system. Furthermore, this emphasizes the need to not only screen for genes in a single tissue but more work should be done on the systemic level.

Conclusion

The vast complexity of this disease may stem from the insistence upon classifying it a neurodegenerative disease. While the evidence to show the debilitating nature of

Huntington's disease in the brain is irrefutable, it has been unsuccessful in explaining the heterogeneity in patient symptoms. As it was reviewed here, there is substantial evidence to demonstrate pathogenic effects outside of the nervous system. Indeed, it has been known for 30 years that huntingtin transcript and protein is localized almost ubiquitously in the body, but by only studying the brain we are only getting half the story⁸⁰⁻⁸³. More studies need to be done that take into consideration the peripheral tissues. There is much potential there, not only in uncovering the underpinnings of this disease, but also diagnostically and therapeutically. Clinically, one of the greatest difficulties with neurodegenerative diseases is the tissue is not easily accessible for biopsy. Instead of disregarding data from peripheral tissues, it should be used to our advantage to identify new biomarkers to assess disease progression and inter-tissue transmission. Together, combining markers across all affected tissues would begin to establish a more complete, systemic picture of the disease.

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Figure 1 Protein architecture of genes that undergo polyglutamine expansion. There are no remarkable similarities between them, besides the polyQ repeats. Schematic is drawn to scale. Numbers denote amino acid residue.

	Transcript	Protein	Aggregates
	not examined	not examined	not examined

Figure 2 Summary of studies on *huntingtin* transcript, protein, and aggregated protein in peripheral tissues. Circular blue symbols from top down are: heart, bone, gut, liver, kidney and adrenal gland, pancreas, adipose tissue, muscle. Symbols in black depict the organism studied. Number above the organisms is the citation to the original study.